

Addition of HCN to imines 8-14 (Table 2) : The appropriate imine (1-7 ; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in methanol and the solution was made acidic by adding a few drops of acetic acid. Potassium cyanide (0.01 mol in 10 ml water) was added to the imine solution with continuous stirring at 0-5°. The product (8-14) obtained was filtered and recrystallised from methanol. 1-4 gave nitriles 8-11, whereas 5-7 yielded nitriles 12-14. The cyanoimines showed the absorption at 3 430 (NH) and 2 245 cm⁻¹ (C≡N).

TABLE 2

Compd. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p °C	Yield %	N% found/Calcd
8	2-OH	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	185	80	10.50 (10.57)
9	4-NO ₂	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	197	67	13.03 (13.14)
10	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	193	75	10.15 (10.21)
11	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	158	70	10.93 (11.02)
12	4-NO ₂	C ₃₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	95	70	12.85 (12.77)
13	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂	135	60	9.75 (9.86)
14	4-Cl	C ₃₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ Cl	173	63	8.90 (8.79)

TABLE 3

Compd no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	N% : Found/Calcd
15	2-OH	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	129	55	7.44 (7.52)
16	4-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	209	50	10.39 (10.47)
17	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	107	56-60	7.17 (7.25)
18	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	169	45	7.79 (7.86)
19	4-NO ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	84	60	9.16 (9.21)
20	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N	115	52	5.32 (5.41)
21	4-Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ NCl	165	56	4.82 (4.77)

The nitro substituted derivative showed the absorption at 1 520 cm⁻¹ which indicates that the NO₂ group does not undergo reduction during the reaction with borohydride.

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Reduction of imines 15-21 with NaBH₄ (Table 3) : Sodium borohydride (0.03 mol) was added to a methanolic solution of the imine (0.02 mol) over a period of 30 min at 5-10°. The mixture was then kept overnight at room temperature. The excess sodium borohydride was neutralised by adding water and the product extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water until neutral, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and finally evaporated. The compound (15-21) thus obtained was recrystallised from methanol. 1-4 gave the dihydro compounds (15-18), whereas 5-7 gave the dihydro compounds 19-21. The dihydro products showed the absorption at 3 300-3 250 cm⁻¹ (NH).

Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of Hydroxyphenylethylidenebenzylamines

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A detailed survey of the literature reveals that there are only a few instances^{1,2} where imines have shown antifungal activity, and most of these imines have at least one halogen atom which

has its own effect. In order to find out whether the imines having no halogen atom are also active against fungus, some ketimines⁸ were synthesised by condensing various ketones with benzylamine. But these imines were found to have little effect against fungus. It has been reported that presence of hydroxyphenyl group in some compounds increases the activity^{4,5}. So it was proposed to synthesise new ketimines having hydroxyphenyl group. This paper describes the synthesis of 2-hydroxyphenylethylidenebenzylamine (1), 4-hydroxyphenylethylidenebenzylamine (2), 2,4-dihydroxyphenylethylidenebenzylamine (3), 2,5-dihydroxyphenylethylidenebenzylamine (4) and 2,6-dihydroxyphenylethylidenebenzylamine (5), their spectral studies and antifungal activity.

2-Hydroxyacetophenone, 4-hydroxyacetophenone, 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone, 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone and 2,6-dihydroxyacetophenone which fail to give imines with aniline and substituted anilines perhaps due to steric hinderance offered by methyl group, yielded crystalline compounds (1-5) with benzylamine in quantitative yields.

The ketimines have been identified and confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies. Uv spectra of these ketimines indicate three absorption bands at 212, 265 and 340 nm. The band at 265 nm is used to identify the azomethine linkage as is shown by the fact that this band completely disappears on reduction of the ketimines with sodium borohydride. Ir spectrum of 1 shows absorption band at ~ 1620 (azomethine) and $\sim 3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (phenolic). The lowering of the absorption value in the former case is attributed to the presence of intra-molecular hydrogen bonding⁹. Nmr spectrum of 1 indicates nine aromatic protons as a multiplet between τ 2.6-3.2, three methyl protons as a singlet at τ 7.7, two methylene protons as a singlet at τ 5.2 and the phenolic proton at τ 1.8 as a singlet. In mass spectra molecular ion peaks constitute the base peaks. Another common and important peak in all the spectra is at 91 which is ascribed to $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2^+$ species. The physical data of the ketimines are recorded in Table 1.

Compd. no.	R	R'	Yield %	M.p.* °C	Molecular formula**
1	H	2-OH	95	110	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$
2	4-OH	2-H	95	135	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$
3	4-OH	2-OH	95	90	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$
4	5-OH	2-OH	90	185	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$
5	6-OH	2-OH	90	115	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$

*Uncorrected. **All gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Antifungal activity: The new ketimines (1-5) were tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria triticina*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Puccinia striiformis*, *Puccinia recondita* and *Pestalotia psidii* by employing standard method of spore germination inhibition. Four concentrations, viz. 1 000, 500, 250 and 100 ppm of each of the compounds have been tried against all the test fungi. All the compounds have been found to possess promising antifungal activity against the above fungi and caused 100% spore germination inhibition at 1 000 ppm. The other three concentrations were also effective (Table 2). Substitution by the second hydroxyl particularly in 6-position, increases the activity of the parent compound.

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF HYDROXYPHENYLETHYLIDENEENZYLAMINES

Comd. no.	Conc ppm	Activity (% spore germination inhibition)				
		A. triticina	A. tenuis	P. striiformis	P. recondita	P. psidii
1	1 000	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	500	100.0	100.0	95.5	96.2	98.2
	250	92.2	69.2	62.1	54.4	47.3
	100	33.2	21.5	17.15	18.4	25.1
2	1 000	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	500	92.7	90.1	80.5	90.0	90.2
	250	63.1	53.4	51.2	47.2	42.2
	100	29.9	20.4	20.6	15.6	32.2
3	1 000	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	500	100.0	100.0	96.1	79.2	82.1
	250	74.2	70.1	69.2	65.2	64.3
	100	35.6	27.9	23.6	17.1	20.1
4	1 000	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	500	100.0	100.0	92.1	100.0	83.3
	250	72.1	73.4	64.2	52.5	55.1
	100	32.3	28.1	20.3	10.3	19.2
5	1 000	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	500	100.0	100.0	97.2	98.7	100.0
	250	81.2	75.9	72.0	62.2	67.3
	100	41.3	36.2	34.7	25.5	31.4

Experimental

The following general procedure was used for the synthesis of hydroxyphenylethylidenebenzylamines.

A mixture of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (0.1 mol), benzylamine (0.1 mol) and toluene (125 ml) was refluxed using a 'Dean and Stark' apparatus. Distillation of the solvent after the azeotropic removal of water formed during the reaction gave the crude ketimine which was recrystallised from ethanol to yield fine yellow crystals of 2-hydroxyphenylethylidenebenzylamine (95%), m.p. 110°.

Testing of the compounds against fungus: Four concentrations (1 000, 500, 250 and 100 ppm) of 1 were taken and treated against *Puccinia striiformis*. The treated spores were incubated for 18 h and per cent spore germination inhibition was calculated by

counting 200 spores of each treatment. Spores incubated in water and respective solvent in which the compound was dissolved were used as control. Percentage spore germination inhibition was calculated using the standard formula. Similarly, other ketimines (2-5) were tested for their antifungal activity against *Puccinia striiformis*, *Puccinia recondita*, *Alternaria tritricina*, *Alternaria tenuis* and *Pestalotia psidii*

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Reaction of Azlactone with Veratraldehyde Schiff Bases

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REACTION of azlactones, which are obtained *in situ* from α -acylamido acids, with carbonyl compounds constitutes a special case of the Perkin reaction. Cinnamalanilines and azlactone of benzoylalanine have been shown to undergo a (4+2)-cycloaddition reaction². In continuation of the work on this reaction with disubstituted benzaldehydes³, this paper describes the reaction of benzoylglycine with veratraldehyde Schiff bases⁴.

A crystalline product, m.p. 162°, was obtained in quantitative yield by the reaction of azlactone, prepared from hippuric acid and acetic anhydride *in situ* in presence of sodium acetate, with 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde. On the basis of elemental analysis, ir and nmr studies, the compound has been identified as 2-phenyl-4-(3,4-dimethoxybenzal)-5-oxazolone (3). Ir spectrum of the product shows absorption bands at 1750 and 1670 cm^{-1} indicative of C=O and C=N linkage, respectively. Nmr spectrum (CDCl_3) of the product indicates 6 methoxy protons at τ 6.0 as a singlet, and a multiplet at τ 2.2-3.4 equivalent to 4 protons thereby showing that olefinic proton merges with the aromatic protons.

It seems, 3 is formed through the electrophilic addition of the enolate, produced by the abstraction of a proton by base from the active methylene part of the azlactone to the Schiff base to give an unstable adduct (2) followed by elimination of amine in the presence of base (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The product 3 is confirmed by m.m.p. determination (no depression) with authentic sample of 2-phenyl-4-(3,4-dimethoxybenzal)-5-oxazolone synthesised by an unambiguous route¹. Electron-donating substituents (*p*-OEt, *p*-OMe, *p*-Me) in the *N*-phenyl nucleus facilitate the reaction as shown by higher yields of the product, whereas electron-withdrawing groups (Cl, Br) retard it. However, the same product was obtained after amine elimination in all the cases.

Experimental

Reaction of azlactone (1) with 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde: Hippuric acid (1.8 g, 0.01 mol) and 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (2.41 g, 0.01 mol) were dissolved in dry benzene (50 ml) and to it acetic anhydride (A.R.; 1.2 ml) added. The mixture was heated and allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 days. During this period most of the crude product separated out which was filtered under reduced pressure. The mother liquor on concentration yielded a further crop. The combined crude product